

SRIL34 DOCUMENTATION

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SRIL34

Configuration of the SRIL34 model. The model domain covers the area around Sri Lanka with approximately 1/60th degree resolution, and is based on GEBCO bathymetry. It uses ERA5 forcing data and Copernicus (CMEMS) reanalysis data.

Repository Content

This repository contains the scripts and initialisation file to run the SRIL34 model (physics only), as well as the SRIL34-ERSEM (passive tracers) configuration. It contains instructions for:

- setting up paths and file directory structure
- compiling xios
- compiling NEMO and tools
- compiling FABM and ERSEM
- setting up the SRIL34 domain
- installing PyNEMO
- creating open boundary conditions
- Creating ERA5 forcing
- running the SRIL34 model.

Getting Started

To get started, clone this repository

`git clone https://github.com/NOC-MSM/SRIL34.git`
then follow the instructions on the [wiki](#)

Welcome to the SRIL34 wiki!

This wiki describes the methods used to configure the SRIL34 model (physics only) and the SRIL34_ERSEM (passive tracers) configurations.

The SRIL34 model domain is of 1/60th degree resolution, based on GEBCO bathymetry. It uses ERA5 forcing data and Copernicus (CMEMS) reanalysis data.

The content of this wiki and the SRIL34 configuration are based on previous work on the [SANH model](#), and [SEAsia model](#). The method used for the domain generation follows that of [GCOMS1k](#). The SRIL34_FABM configuration coupled to one ERSEM module for passive tracers simulation mainly follows that of the [AMM7-NEMO4-FABM setup](#), but using the [ERSEMyuti repository](#) (this is a private page, you may not have access. The equivalent public repository is available [here](#), rather than standard ERSEM.

1.A Setting up SRIL34

Set paths

To build the NEMO, XIOS, and Tool needed to run the SRIL34 model, navigate to the SRIL34_physics/SCRIPTS/ in the bash terminal (see files [here](#)) and edit make_paths.sh as necessary ((likely only the \$CONFIG and \$WORK paths, and the path to the \$EXTRA containing the [EXTRA TOOLS](#) files if you want to compile the nemo tools). Then, run the following scripts in order. Note that these routines have been used on Archer2.

```
cd SRIL34_physics/SCRIPTS/  
. ./make_paths.sh  
. ./make_directories.sh  
. ./make_xios.sh  
. ./make_nemo.sh
```

These are made before the domain file so some of the tooling and directory structures can be reused.

Compile XIOS

After running make_paths.sh and make_directories.sh, view the make_xios.sh script. Navigate to your \$WDIR and load the necessary modules (they might change to depending on your HPC):

```
cd $WDIR  
module swap craype-network-ofi craype-network-ucx  
module swap cray-mpich cray-mpich-ucx  
module load cray-hdf5-parallel/1.12.0.7  
module load cray-netcdf-hdf5parallel/4.7.4.7
```

Download XIOS:

```
svn checkout http://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/ioserver/svn/XIOS/branches/xios-2.5 $XIOS_DIR  
cd $XIOS_DIR
```

Copy over the necessary [arch](#) files and compile:

```
cp /work/n01/shared/nemo/xios-2.5/arch/arch-X86_ARCHER2-Cray.* arch/  
./make_xios --prod --arch X86_ARCHER2-Cray --netcdf_lib netcdf4_par --full --job 4
```

Note, the first time will fail. You will have to change the FC flag

in \$XIOS_DIR/tools/FCM/lib/Fcm/Config.pm and recompile:

```
sed -i "s/FC_MODSEARCH => ''/FC_MODSEARCH => '-J'/g" tools/FCM/lib/Fcm/Config.pm  
./make_xios --prod --arch X86_ARCHER2-Cray --netcdf_lib netcdf4_par --full --job 4  
cd $SCRIPTS
```

Compile NEMO

The script to compile NEMO is similar to the one used for building XIOS. Open the make_nemo.sh script and download NEMO:

```
cd $WDIR
```

```
svn co http://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/nemo/svn/NEMO/branches/UKMO/NEMO_4.0.4_mirror
NEMO_4.0.4
```

Comment out this download line after it has been download (to avoid overwriting files).

Load modules (these may change depending on your HPC):

```
module load craype-network-ucx
module load cray-mpich-ucx
module load cray-hdf5-parallel/1.12.0.7
module load cray-netcdf-hdf5parallel/4.7.4.7
```

Then copy over the [arch](#) file for your HPC and edit some of the configuration parameters:

```
cp $GITCLONE/arch-X86_ARCHER2-Cray.fcm $NEMO/arch/arch-X86_ARCHER2-Cray.fcm

cd $NEMO
sed -i "s/FC_MODSEARCH => ''/FC_MODSEARCH => '-J'/g" ext/FCM/lib/Fcm/Config.pm
```

Compile NEMO:

```
cd $NEMO
./makenemo -n $CONFIG -r AMM12 -m X86_ARCHER2-Cray -j 16
```

Copy over the [keys](#) and the [MY_SRC](#) directory (These are configured for the [SANH](#) model configuration, they are identical to those used for the **physics only** SRIL34 model):

```
cd $CDIR/$CONFIG
cp $GITCLONE/cpp_SANH.fcm cpp_$CONFIG.fcm
cp -r -f $GITCLONE/MY_SRC ./
```

Finally, clean and recompile NEMO with the updates included:

```
cd $NEMO
./makenemo -r $CONFIG -m X86_ARCHER2-Cray -j 16 clean
./makenemo -r $CONFIG -m X86_ARCHER2-Cray -j 16
cd $SCRIPTS
```

Install miniconda

Miniconda is needed for python preprocessing, specifically for using PyNEMO (for generation of the boundary conditions).

```
cd /work/n01/n01/<user>
wget https://repo.continuum.io/miniconda/Miniconda3-latest-Linux-x86_64.sh
chmod u+x Miniconda3-latest-Linux-x86_64.sh
./Miniconda3-latest-Linux-x86_64.sh
```

Install in `/work/n01/n01/$USER/miniconda3` when prompted.

Allow it to modify `PYTHONPATH` in `.bashrc` Close and open shell

Compiling the NEMO tools

To compile the NEMO tools, use the script: `make_tools.sh`.

First, load the modules (these will vary depending on your machine), and copy over an edited [DOMAINzgr](#) source code file (adjusted to include more varied vertical coordinates) into the NEMO tools directory:

```
module swap craype-network-ofi craype-network-ucx
module swap cray-mpich cray-mpich-ucx
module load cray-hdf5-parallel/1.12.0.7
module load cray-netcdf-hdf5parallel/4.7.4.7
```

```
# Make an adjustment to the DOMAINcfg source code to accomodate more varied vertical
coords
cp $EXTRA/DOMAIN/domzgr.f90.melange $TDIR/DOMAINcfg/src/domzgr.f90
```

Then, apply the necessary [patches](#) to the weight file code:

```
cd $NEMO/tools/WEIGHTS/src
patch -b < $EXTRA/patch_files/scripinterp_mod.patch
patch -b < $EXTRA/patch_files/scripinterp.patch
patch -b < $EXTRA/patch_files/scrip.patch
patch -b < $EXTRA/patch_files/scripshape.patch
patch -b < $EXTRA/patch_files/scripgrid.patch
```

And finally compile the NEMO tools:

```
cd $NEMO/tools
./maketools -m X86_ARCHER2-Cray -n NESTING
./maketools -m X86_ARCHER2-Cray -n REBUILD_NEMO
./maketools -m X86_ARCHER2-Cray -n WEIGHTS
./maketools -m X86_ARCHER2-Cray -n DOMAINcfg
```

```
cd $WORK
```

1.B Setting up SRIL34_FABM

This pages shows how to set up the SRIL34-FABM configuration. This configuration couples the SRIL34 model to one module of ERSEM (*!not the full ERSEM!*) though FABM, allowing simulation of a passive tracer. The configuration is very similar to that of the [SRIL34 physics only](#), but there are some differences in the setup and keys used for the coupling. These instructions are specific to the SRIL34 model but more information on configurations coupling NEMO to FABM can be found [here](#).

Set paths

First of all, go to you workspace, eg. `/work/n01/n01/<USER>/` and create the directory you want to work in eg. `mkdir SRIL_FABM`. You can choose whichever file structure you prefer, in the examples below we created a separate `code` directory to store all that relates to the codes. To get started, set the environment and working paths running the [set_paths.sh](#). In this example the configuration is called `SANH_FABM`, as it can be used for both the `SANH` and `SRIL34` model. Change the paths to the directories you want to work in. **Always run this before running any scripts.**

```
export CONFIG=SANH_FABM
export WORK=/work/n01/n01/<USER>/SRIL_FABM
export CODE_DIR=$WORK/code
```

Clone repositories

You now need to clone the correct XIOS, NEMO, FABM and ERSEM repositories. This will get you the files you need to be able to install the programs in the next step. Again, you can clone the repositories wherever you prefer, here we created four subdirectories inside `$WORK/code`:

```
mkdir $CODE_DIR/xios
mkdir $CODE_DIR/ersem
mkdir $CODE_DIR/fabm
mkdir $CODE_DIR/nemo
```

Once you directories are set, run the [clone_repositories.sh](#) script.

NOTE: In this example I clone the [ERSEM-yuti](#) repository rather than the standard ERSEM, from a private page as the public version was not available at the time. The current public version of this ERSEM repository is now available [here](#).

```
XIOS_DIR=$CODE_DIR/xios
svn checkout http://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/ioserver/svn/XIOS/branches/xios-2.5 $XIOS_DIR
```

```
ERSEM_DIR=$CODE_DIR/ersem
git clone https://github.com/yutiPML/ersem-yuti.git $ERSEM_DIR
```

```
FABM_DIR=$CODE_DIR/fabm
git clone https://github.com/fabm-model/fabm.git $FABM_DIR
```

```
NEMO_DIR=$CODE_DIR/nemo
git clone https://github.com/pmlmodelling/NEMO4.0-FABM.git $NEMO_DIR
```

You now have everything you need to compile.

*IMPORTANT: XIOS and FABM must be compiled **before** NEMO*

Compile XIOS

To compile the XIOS, you need to run the [make_xios_cray.sh](#). This will load the modules than you need to compile on archer2

```
module swap craype-network-ofi craype-network-ucx
module swap cray-mpich cray-mpich-ucx
module load cray-hdf5-parallel/1.12.0.7
module load cray-netcdf-hdf5parallel/4.7.4.7
export the directories for the installation of XIOS
```

```
XIOS_DIR=$CODE_DIR/xios
XIOS_INSTALL=$CODE_DIR/xios-cray
cd $XIOS_DIR
```

add the [xios architecture files](#) and the [Config.pm](#) file.

```
# Copy arch files
cp $CODE_DIR/extra-files/xios/arch-X86_ARCHER2-Cray* $XIOS_DIR/arch/
cp $CODE_DIR/extra-files/xios/Config_cray.pm $XIOS_DIR/tools/FCM/lib/Fcm/Config.pm
```

NOTE: in the example these files were cloned from the [AMM7 NEMO FABM git extra-files](#). You will need to change the `$CODE_DIR/extra-files/xios/` depending on where you get the files from. In this git the xios arch files are [here](#), while the `Config.pm` file is [here](#).

Then, Compile the XIOS:

```
export CC=cc export CXX=CC export FC=ftn export F77=ftn export F90=ftn
cd $XIOS_DIR && ./make_xios --prod --arch X86_ARCHER2-Cray --netcdf_lib netcdf4_par --job
16 --full
rsync -a $XIOS_DIR/bin $XIOS_DIR/inc $XIOS_DIR/lib $XIOS_INSTALL
cd $WORK
```

Compile FABM and ERSEM

To compile FABM and ERSEM (*NOTE: only one ERSEM module is used in this configuration*) you need to run the [make_fabm_cray.sh](#) script.

This will first load an additional module:

```
module load cmake
```

make sure that the same modules you used to compile xios are still loaded (you can check with the command `module list`), if not load them:

```
module swap craype-network-ofi craype-network-ucx
module swap cray-mpich cray-mpich-ucx
module load cray-hdf5-parallel/1.12.0.7
module load cray-netcdf-hdf5parallel/4.7.4.7
```

export the directories for the installation (note that the ersem and fabm directories should already exist, so you are only exporting them, while the fabm-cray directory is created now).

```
ERSEM_DIR=$CODE_DIR/ersem
FABM_DIR=$CODE_DIR/fabm
FABM_INSTALL=$CODE_DIR/fabm-cray
```

```
mkdir $FABM_INSTALL
```

the move into the FABM_INSTALL directory for the installation, and compile:

```
cd $FABM_INSTALL
cmake $FABM_DIR/src -DFABM_HOST=nemo -DFABM_ERSEM_BASE=$ERSEM_DIR -DFABM_EMBED_VERSION=ON -
DCMAKE_INSTALL_PREFIX=$FABM_INSTALL -DCMAKE_Fortran_COMPILER=ftn #-DCMAKE_BUILD_TYPE=debug
make
make install -j4
```

```
cd $WORK
```

Compile NEMO

*IMPORTANT: NEMO must be compiled **after** XIOS and FABM*

Finally, the last thing you have to compile is NEMO; to do this use the script [make_nemo_cray.sh](#).

Make sure that the correct modules are loaded. If you have just compiled XIOS and FABM they should already be, if not load them:

```
module load cmake

module swap craype-network-ofi craype-network-ucx
module swap cray-mpich cray-mpich-ucx
module load cray-hdf5-parallel/1.12.0.7
module load cray-netcdf-hdf5parallel/4.7.4.7
```

Then export the directories you need and move into your \$NEMO_DIR directory before installing:

```
export FABM_HOME=$CODE_DIR/fabm-cray
export XIOS_HOME=$CODE_DIR/xios-cray
NEMO_DIR=$CODE_DIR/nemo
cd $NEMO_DIR
```

Copy the [Config.pm](#) file in your Fcm directory:

```
cp $CODE_DIR/extra-files/nemo/Config_cray.pm $NEMO_DIR/ext/FCM/lib/Fcm/Config.pm
```

Before compiling, make sure that in the config.pm you have the line `FC_MODSEARCH => '-J',`. It is possible that you have `FC_MODSEARCH => ''`, instead; if this is the case, edit it to be `FC_MODSEARCH => '-J',`.

*NOTE: in the example the \$CODE_DIR/extra-files/** directory was cloned from the [AMM7 NEMO FABM git extra-files](#). You will need to change the path depending on where you are copying the files from. In this wiki the config.pm file is [here](#).*

Then, export the directories:

```
CFG=SANH_FABM  
ARCH=X86_ARCHER2-Cray_FABM  
REF=AMM7_FABM
```

and, making sure you are still in the \$NEMO_DIR directory, compile NEMO and get back in your main work space:

```
printf 'y\n\n\nny\n\n\n\n\n\n' |./makenemo -n $CFG -r $REF -m $ARCH -j 0  
./makenemo -n $CFG -r $REF -m $ARCH -j 4 clean  
./makenemo -n $CFG -r $REF -m $ARCH -j 4
```

```
cd $WORK
```

2. Create the Domain

Generate coordinates and Bathymetry files

To generate the `domain_cfg.nc` you first need to create the a coordinates file `coordinates.nc` and a bathymetry file `bathy_meter.nc`. For the SRIL34 domain, this is done using the GridBuilder matlab toolbox. To install it and use grid builder, follow the instruction in the [make_grid.txt](#):

on livljobs8, cd into the directory you want to work from and download Gridbuilder:

```
#Download GridBuilder
wget https://austides.com/wp-content/uploads/GridBuilder\_toolbox.mltbx
```

To install it, open matlab and click on the `GridBuilder_toolbox.mltbx`:

```
#Open matlab:
module load matlab
matlab
```

```
#When in matlab, click on
GridBuilder_toolbox.mltbx to install
```

You then need to modify one of the GridBuilder's functions to allow it to read NetCDF files. To do this, still in matlab, check the Add-Ons location in the preferences. The path should look something like this:

```
#Check Add-Ons location in Preferences:
~/Documents/MATLAB/Add-Ons/Toolboxes/
```

Then copy the [getUserBathymetry.m](#) to the GridBuilder's functions:

```
#Add a trick to allow Gridbuilder to read *.nc files:
cp getUserBathymetry.m ~/Documents/MATAB/Add-Ons/Toolboxes/Gridbuilder/Functions/
```

then modify the paths in [environment.m](#) and run it to set you path.

in matlab's command window type: `GridBuilder`

This will open up the Gridbuilder GUI. From there, go to

File --> Import --> Bathymetry

and select your bathymetry file (in this case, it'ss `LME_32_34_GEBCO_bathy.nc`).

Draw your grid on the map, starting from the bottom left-hand corner (more stable this way). **Change the resolution of your grid in the box at the top** . You can rotate the grid using the "Grid Edit" tools on the right hand side of the GUI When happy with your grid, go to Mask Settings and choose GSHHC Coastlines (this takes a while so should be your last step). Save your grid using a unique identifier e.g. [SRIL34_Grid.mat](#) (SRIL34 stands for Sri Lanka in LME number 34).

Now you have your grid, open [GridBuilder to NEMO.m](#). In this script, `DOMNAM` is the unique identifier you used (e.g. SRIL34). Change the `grid_path` to reflect the location of your saved

grid file, and change the domain paths to reflect your directories (*NOTE: the assessment path is not called in this script*).

Run the MATLAB script.

This should output your chosen grid in NEMO compatible files:

```
SRIL34_bathy_meter.nc
```

```
SRIL34_coordinates.nc
```

This files will then be used to create the domain_cfg.nc file

Generate the domain_cfg.nc

The domain generation is done on archer. Move the bathymetry and coordinate files you have just created in an archer2 directory (eg: using scp). *IMPORTANT: for this work you need to already have compiled NEMO and tool*

cd into the directory where you have put your bathymetry and coordinate files. Copy the namelist_cfg from your NEMO tools. Eg:

```
cp /work/n01/n01/<user>/SANH/NEMO_4.0.4/tools/DOMAINcfg/namelist_cfg .
```

Now, find out your domain size by dumping the bathymetry file (eg: ncdump -h bathy_meter.nc) and edit namelist_cfg for domain size:

```
vi namelist_cfg
```

then change the dimensions (in this case 324,424,50)

```
jpjtdta      =    324  ! 1st lateral dimension ( >= jpi )
jpkdta       =    424  ! 2nd      "           "   ( >= jpj )
jpkdta       =     50  ! number of levels      ( >= jpk )
jpiglo       =    324  ! 1st dimension of global domain --> i =jpjtdta
jjpglo       =    424  ! 2nd
```

now creat symbolic links to all other files that you need contain in your NEMO tool directory. These are the *.xml* files, the namelist_ref, and the executable. Eg:

```
ln -s /work/n01/n01/<user>/SANH/NEMO_4.0.4/tools/DOMAINcfg/*.xml .
```

```
ln -s /work/n01/n01/<user>/SANH/NEMO_4.0.4/tools/DOMAINcfg/namelist_ref .
```

```
ln -s /work/n01/n01/<user>/SANH/NEMO_4.0.4/tools/DOMAINcfg/make_domain_cfg.exe .
```

you should now have the bathymetry file, the coordinate file, the namelist_cfg, and the (symbolic) *.xml, namelist_ref and executable in the same directory.

Run the domain_cfg tools using the [make_domain.slurm](#) (for archer2):

```
sbatch make_domain.slurm
```

Note: remember to change the account name and time before running it

3. Download CMEMS Data

Downloading daily Copernicus (CMEMS) data

This page details how to download daily CMEMS data for each year. As the bulk of the CMEMS data is used for PyNEMO, we download them using one of the local livljobs servers.

1. Create motu environment

If you do not already have one, create an account on [Copernicus](#). CMEMS data can be downloaded using the [motu client](#), for which you need to create a python environment. Load the latest anaconda module on livljobs (here anaconda/5-2021), and create an environment. Note that motu client only works with **python v3**, make sure you are creating an environment that uses one of these.

```
module load anaconda/5-2021
conda create --name motu_env
activate your environment and install the motu client
```

```
conda activate motu_env
```

```
conda install pip
pip install motuclient
```

Note that you can activate and deactivate your environment using `conda activate motu_env` and `conda deactivate`

2. Download CMEMS data

For SRIL34, you will need to download: -temperature -salinity -sea surface height -U velocity component -V velocity components

from the Global Reanalysis product (GLOBAL_REANALYSIS_PHY_001_030).

An example of how to download an individual day (e.g. 1st Jan 1993) is:

```
python -m motuclient --motu http://my.cmems-du.eu/motu-web/Motu --service-id
GLOBAL_REANALYSIS_PHY_001_030-TDS --product-id global-reanalysis-phy-001-030-daily --
longitude-min 50 --longitude-max 115 --latitude-min -10 --latitude-max 30 --date-min "1993-
01-01 12:00:00" --date-max "1993-01-01 12:00:00" --depth-min 0.493 --depth-max
5727.918000000001 --variable thetao --variable so --variable zos --out-name
"CMEMS_1993_01_01_download.nc" --user USERNAME --pwd PASSWORD
```

USERNAME and PASSWORD are your individual credentials that you use to log in to your Copernicus account.

To download an entire year, use the scripts [download CMEMS.sh](#) (for salinity, temperature and ssh), and the scrip [download CMEMS UV.sh](#) (for U and V velocity components). These are modified versions of annkat's SEAsia scripts for downloading CMEMS data. Edit the script for the year you want to download, and the scripts will automatically download each day in

that year (*NOTE that it doesn't include the 29th Feb for leap years so this has to be downloaded separately*).

At the bottom of each script there are two more daily data requests for the last and first day of the previous and subsequent years (e.g. for 1993, there will be extra requests for 31st Dec 1992 and 1st Jan 1994). Manually edit the dates for the ones you want to download.

Create the directories which you want to store the data in, eg. `mkdir CMEMS_data`, and run both scripts separately to download data. You can either run both script manually (*!one at the time, not simultaneously!*) or run the script [Pynemo workflow 1.sh](#).

```
./Pynemo_workflow_1.sh
```

This subsequently runs `download_CMEMS.sh` and `download_CMEMS_UV.sh` in turn and stores output files in your directory. Make sure you are in the directory in which the data are stored eg. `CMEMS_data`. This script also generates two text files (`Download1.txt` and `Download2.txt`) which output the terminal messages for each download script. It also allows you to check more easily if any data is missing as shown in the next step.

ATTENTION: Downloading CMEMS data takes a long time (>5 hrs per year). The Copernicus system can only cope with one data request per user at a time, so don't run both the scripts together

3. Checking any data omissions

There have been consistent issues with data file omissions. To spot which files are missing, you can use the `*.txt` files for the CMEMS downloads.

First, navigate to the directory you stored the temp, sal and ssh files in, e.g.:

```
cd CMEMS_data
```

Then see how many files have been downloaded using the command:

```
ls -l . | egrep -c '^-'
```

There should be 367 files in the directory (368 if its a leap year). If any files are missing, they will need to be download individually.

The `Download1.txt` (CMEMS temp, sal, ssh) and `Download2.txt` (U,V) contain the log of all data being downloaded. Search the files for any dates that have an `ERROR`. Do this for all years and manually download the missing files into the appropriate directory.

NOTE: I've usually found that missing files bunch up, so you're likely to get subsequent omissions

4. Create Open Boundary Conditions

Generate the open boundary conditions (OBC) using Copernicus (CMEMS) data

To generate the OBC with the CMEMS data downloaded, you will need to use [PyNEMO](#). You can use this tool on the livljobs servers or you can directly [install PyNEMO on Archer2](#). Here we show the steps to download and use PyNEMO on Archer2.

1. Install miniconda (only for archer2)

If you followed the [setting up SRIL34](#) instructions, you should already have miniconda installed on archer2. If not, log into Archer2, and cd into your working directory. Here, install miniconda.

```
cd /work/n01/n01/<user>
wget https://repo.continuum.io/miniconda/Miniconda3-latest-Linux-x86_64.sh
chmod u+x Miniconda3-latest-Linux-x86_64.sh
./Miniconda3-latest-Linux-x86_64.sh
```

Install in `/work/n01/n01/$USER/miniconda3` when prompted.
Allow it to modify PYTHONPATH in `.bashrc`. Close and open shell.

NOTE: you do not need to install miniconda on livljobs to use PyNEMO. This step is only to use it on Archer2.

2. Install PyNEMO

In your working directory, clone the PyNEMO repository:

```
$ cd /work/n01/n01/$USER
$ git clone https://github.com/NOC-MSM/PyNEMO.git
```

Cloning the repository will generate a `PyNEMO` directory containing the repository files, including the `pynemo_39.yml`. This file specifies the modules needed to run PyNEMO and is used to create the right conda environment for it. Move into the directory and create a conda environment specifically for PyNEMO.

```
$ cd PyNEMO
$ conda env create -f pynemo_39.yml
```

Activate your environment to install PyNEMO:

```
$ source activate pynemo
```

On Archer2, your Java path should already be set, however if for any reason it's not, this might cause issues. If you have issues, you can check your path using `$ whereis java`, and export the correct java path **if needed**. You will probably be able to skip this step.

NOTE: if you are on livljobs, you will need to check what the latest java path is to use and export it.

```
$ export JAVA_HOME=/usr/lib64/jvm/java
```

You should now be in your PyNEMO directory (/work/n01/n01/\$USER/PyNEMO) with your pynemo environment activated. Install PyNEMO with:

```
python setup.py build
export PYTHONPATH=/home/n01/n01/$USER/miniconda3/envs/pynemo/lib/python3.9/site-
packages:$PYTHONPATH
python setup.py install
```

you can check that the installation worked using

```
$ pynemo -h
```

which should result in a help usage prompt message similar to:

```
usage: pynemo [-g] -s <namelist.bdy>
       -g (optional) will open settings editor before extracting the data
       -s <bdy filename> file to use
```

NOTE: it is possible you also see the note 'Didn't find a proxy environment variable' along with the help usage prompt. This doesn't mean your installation went wrong.

3. Use PyNEMO

To use pynemo you will first need to gather a bunch of files used by the program. You need:

- The domain file from the model you want to create OBC for (here for eg. SRIL34).
- The bathymetry file from the model you want to create OBC for.
- A coordinates file from you parent model (here for eg. CMEMS, which can be downloaded as explained [here](#)).
- A file called [inputs_src.ncml](#) which contains the location of the parent coordinates file and defines some of the parent model variable names.
- A file called [inputs_dst.ncml](#) which is used to rename some variables.
- You might need a mask file for you subdomain (*not needed if you only want tidal boundary condition*).
- Another ncml file setting the paths to your parent model and some of its variable. Usually this is one file per year (eg [CMEMS 2014.ncml](#)). *NOTE: there are two separate paths to be defined in the file, one for the CMEMS file containing salinity/temperature, and one for the CMEMS file containing the U, V current.*
- FES tide data, if running tides (*NOTE: these are on shared location on both archer2 and livljobs, you only really need the paths*)

Finally, to run pynemo you will then need a namelist file defines the variables that you are using. You can amend this file to run tidal boundary conditions, open boundary conditions, or both (eg. [namelist SRIL34.dby](#), or [namelist FES14 Archer.bdy](#)).

Make sure that you namelist file (`namelist_SRIL34.dby`), and your three ncml files (`inputs_src_zgr.ncml` , `inputs_dst.ncml`, `CMEMS_2014.ncml`) are set for the right dates and pointing to the right directories. Also set your output directories where you want to save files.

Then, to run PyNEMO use the command:

```
$ pynemo -s /path/to/namelist/file (eg. pynemo -s namelist_SRIL34.dby)
```

5. Create ERA5 forcing

Downloading ERA5 data.

To create the ERA5 forcing you first need to download some ERA5 data. The following step explain how to do this on NOC's server (*livjobs*).

ERA5 data are stored in NOC under `/projectsa/NEMO/Forcing/ERA5/SURFACE_FORCING` . Before you download new data, check that what you need isn't already in this shared directory (it probably is).

If not, you will need to first create an account on [CDS](#) (if you do not already have one), then install the [cdsapi](#) python package and add your security key.

The next step is to run the script [Download viaCDS ERA5 Global PerVariable.py](#) (saved in *livjobs* under the `/projectsa/NEMO/Forcing/Download_viaCDS_ERA5_Global_PerVariable.py`) to download ERA5 data.

Adapt the script by changing the dates and variables you need to download (you can make a copy of the script and run it from your directory).

NOTE: The script is set to automatically download data in `/projectsa/NEMO/Forcing/ERA5/SURFACE_FORCING`. If unsure, this can be modified in the script. Please, don't change this in the original script, make a copy.

More detailed instructions on how to download the ERA5 data are available [here](#).

Generate ERA5 forcing

To generate the forcing for the SRIL34 (on NOC's server, *livjobs*), you will need to activate a python environment that has the numpy libraries installed (eg. `nrct_env_py3`).

```
module load anaconda
source activate nrct_env_py3
```

and load the module

```
module load nco/gcc/4.4.2
```

NOTE: This is an updated module and is subsequently switched back to `nco/gcc/4.4.2.ncwa` in the main code

Then, you need to amend the `USR_PARAMS` in the script [OFFICIAL Generate NEMO Forcing NEWERA.py](#), to set the correct dates and paths. The coordinates should already be set for the SRIL34 domain as below (IMPORTANT: The extracted region has to be larger than your model domain size). The `path_EXTRACT` and `path_FORCING` needs to be changed to the directories where you want to extract data and output the forcing. The `path_ERA5` should remain the same.

```
#===== USR_PARAMS =====
```

```

Year_init      = 2019                                ## First year to process
Year_end      = 2019                                ## Last one [included]
East          = 115                                  ## East Border
West          = 50                                   ## West Border
North         = 40                                   ## North Border
South         = -10                                  ## South Border
path_ERA5     = '/projectsa/NEMO/Forcing/ERA5/SURFACE_FORCING/' ## ROOT PATH OD ERA5 DATA
path_EXTRACT  = '/<PathToDir>/EXTRACT_TEST/'          ## WHERE TO EXTRACT YOUR REGION
path_FORCING  = '/<PathToDir>/FORCING_TEST/'          ## NEMO
FORCING

```

Now you should be able to run the script:

```
python OFFICIAL_Generate_NEMO_Forcing_NEWERA.py
```

NOTE: the original scripts for a generic domain is also on livljobs under /projectsa/NEMO/Forcing/Download_viaCDS_ERA5_Global_PerVariable.py or on github [here](#). If you use these, make sure you change the coordinates to those of your domain.

Once all your scripts are set, you can use the [create forcing.sh](#) script to go through all the above steps in one go.

Create weights for atmospheric forcing

To generate the weights, transfer the ERA5 forcing that you have just generated to Archer2, into your \$SBC directory and move into that directory. Then link your coordinates file to the \$SBC directory:

```
ln -s $DOMAIN/coordinates.nc ./
```

Copy over the [required namelists](#) and edit them to reflect your pathnames:

```
cp $GITCLONE/FORCING/namelist_reshape_bicubic_atmos ./
cp $GITCLONE/FORCING/namelist_reshape_bilin_atmos ./
```

also copy the [job create forcing.slurm](#) into the \$SBC directory. Amend the script by replacing the \$TDIR/ to the full path directory. This script (last tested august 2022) will first load modules:

```
module swap craype-network-ofi craype-network-ucx
module swap cray-mpich cray-mpich-ucx
module load cray-hdf5-parallel/1.12.0.7
module load cray-netcdf-hdf5parallel/4.7.4.7
```

Then it will generate the weights for the forcing data (ERA5 in this example) using the SCRIP tools in NEMO:

```
$TDIR/WEIGHTS/scripgrid.exe namelist_reshape_bilin_atmos
$TDIR/WEIGHTS/scrip.exe namelist_reshape_bilin_atmos
$TDIR/WEIGHTS/scripshape.exe namelist_reshape_bilin_atmos
$TDIR/WEIGHTS/scrip.exe namelist_reshape_bicubic_atmos
$TDIR/WEIGHTS/scripshape.exe namelist_reshape_bicubic_atmos
```

NOTE: the SCRIP tools are generated when you [compile the NEMO tools](#)

To run the script submit the `job_create_forcing.sh` using:

```
sbatch job_create_forcing.sh
```

6. Running the models

Running SRIL34 physics

To run the model, first copy you NEMO and XIOS executables in the directory you want to run the model from, for eg:

```
cp /work/n01/n01/<user>/<path_to_nemo_compile>/NEMO_4.0.4/cfgs/<configuration_name>/BLD/bin/nemo.exe .
cp /work/n01/n01/<user>/<path_to_xios_compile>/xios-2.5/bin/xios_server.exe .
```

Now rename the NEMO executable, as archer2 has issues reading the *.exe appendix. **IMPORTANT: only rename the executable that you copied in your running directory!**

```
cd /<run_directory>
mv nemo.exe nemo
```

To run the model you must have your executables nemo and xios.exe, the domain_cfg.nc, the coordinates.nc , in your running directory, together with the *.xml file (that should come up when you compile nemo), your namelist_ref and your namelist_cfg, for eg :

```
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 109310 Nov 4 2021 namelist_ref
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 1702 Nov 4 2021 context_nemo.xml
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 12948 Nov 4 2021 domain_def_nemo.xml
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 110461 Nov 4 2021 field_def_nemo-oce.xml
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 4420 Nov 4 2021 file_def_nemo-oce.xml
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 6922 Nov 4 2021 grid_def_nemo.xml
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 1156 Nov 4 2021 iodef.xml
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 22089760 Nov 3 2021 nemo
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 12331336 Nov 3 2021 xios_server.exe
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 20006632 Nov 2 2021 coordinates.nc
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 642521292 Nov 2 2021 domain_cfg.nc
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 62306 Dec 22 2021 namelist_cfg
```

Amend the [namelist_cfg](#) with the paths to your boundary conditions, and restart files (or initial conditions). Also, set the parameters of the run.

Now all is set-up, you can run the model using a [slurm script](#). To create the slurm script, see archer's instruction. An example of what you might run on your command line (changing the n01_SANH to your account name) is:

```
/work/n01/shared/nemo/mkslurm_hetjob -S 2 -s 8 -m 2 -C 75 -g 4 -N 128 -t 00:10:00 -a n01-SANH -j TEST > TEST.slurm
```

to run it use:

```
sbatch TEST.slurm
```

Running SRIL34_FABM

Generate tracer scenarios

Daily

To generate the passive tracer release scenarios use the script [create_scenario.python](#). This will generate a NetCDF file with daily information on the tracer release (in this example urea) which will be read in by the model.

To generate your scenario, activate your conda environment first (eg. `nrct_env_py3`). On `livjobs`, use:

```
module load anaconda
conda activate nrct_env_py3
```

Amend the `create_scenario.python` to set up your scenario. The script is set to generate a file starting from 2021-01-01 00:00:00 UTC. From this date, you choose the day in which the tracers start being release `day0s`, the duration of the leak in number of days `leak_durations`, the amount of tracer being released `total_tonnes` and the conversion factor to from tonnes to mmol (eg. urea). Also choose the coordinates of the tracer release location (based on the SRIL34 domain), and chose the output file name for you release scenario.

NOTE: the conversion factor will change depending on the molar mass of the chemical you are simulating. For urea, this is 60.06g/mol

```
ntracers=1 # number of tracers to generate
day0s=array([144],dtype=int) # first day of leak for each tracer (144=25 May)
leak_durations=array([1],dtype=int) # duration of the leak for each tracer in days
total_tonnes=array([1100.]) # total mass in tonnes for each of the tracer
conversion_factors=array([16650016.65]) # tonnes to mmol (=1e9/60.06) - Urea

Yindex=array([153],dtype=int) # Lat index per each tracer leak
Xindex=array([102],dtype=int) # Lon index per each tracer leak

name='Scenario_urea1100_leak1day.nc'
```

Once your scenario is ready, run the script with:

```
python create_scenario.python
```

You should now have a 365 days scenarios file. Upload this in your running directory (on Archer2). The file is read in by the model through the [fabm_input.nml](#); make sure you have the right Scenario name here before running the model. Also, as your file is daily, make sure the frequency is of 24 hours.

```
!           ! file name ! frequency (hours) ! variable ! time interp. ! clim !
'yearly'/ ! weights ! rotation ! land/sea mask !
!           !           ! (if <0 months) ! name ! (logical) ! (T/F) !
'monthly' ! filename ! pairing ! filename !
&variable
  name='T1_flux/flux'
```

```
sn=          'Scenario_urea1100_leak1day.nc',24,'T1_flux', .false., .true., 'yearly',
'',          '',          ''
```

Hourly

to simulate tracer releases that occur in less than a daily, you will need to generate and hourly tracer scenario release. To do this use the script [create_scenario_hourly.python](#). This is essentially the same as `create_scenario.python`, but with some changes to express everything in hours, rather than days. This means that when you change the script to set up your scenario, you will need to set the start time of you tracer release, and the duration of the leak in hours rather than days. eg, to set a scenario where the passive tracers are released in 6 hours:

```
ntracers=1                # number of tracers to generate
day0s=array([144*24],dtype=int) # first day of leak for each tracer (144=25 May)
leak_durations=array([6],dtype=int) # duration of the leak for each tracer in hours
total_tonnes=array([1100.]) # total mass in tonnes for each of the tracer
conversion_factors=array([16650016.65]) # tonnes to mmol (=1e9/60.06) - Urea

Yindex=array([153],dtype=int) # Lat index per each tracer leak
Xindex=array([102],dtype=int) # Lon index per each tracer leak

name='Scenario_urea1100_leak6hour.nc'
```

Also, before running the model, make sure that you amend `frequency` in the `fabm_input.nml` to read in the scenario in hours rather than days.

```
!           ! file name ! frequency (hours) ! variable ! time interp. ! clim !
'yearly'/ ! weights ! rotation ! land/sea mask !
!           !           ! (if <0 months) ! name ! (logical) ! (T/F) !
'monthly' ! filename ! pairing ! filename !
&variable
  name='T1_flux/flux'
  sn=          'Scenario_urea1100_leak6hour.nc',1,'T1_flux', .false., .true., 'yearly',
'',          '',          ''
```

Physics and tracer namelists

To run the SRIL34-FABM coupled configuration, the first step are the same as for the physics only (described above). You need to copy the `nemo` and `xios` executable in your running directory, and change the physics `namelist_cfg` in the same way you would change the physics only model.

You will need to make sure that your SANH_FABM configuration is using the right keys. To check, open the `/cfigs/SANH_FABM/cpp_SANH_FABM.fcm` file (saved where you compiled `nemo`) with `vi cpp_SANH_FABM.fcm`. They keys should be:

```
bld::tool::fppkeys  key_mpp_mpi key_vectopt_loop key_nosignedzero key_iomput key_top
key_fabm
```

if this is not the case, add them to the file.

You will need extra *.xml files your directory compared to the physics only. This is a list of what your .xml should look like:

```
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 1912 Apr 28 15:49 context_nemo.xml
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 12948 Apr 28 15:49 domain_def_nemo.xml
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 309 May 4 13:52 field_def_custom.xml
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 3787 Sep 1 12:46 field_def_fabm.xml
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 110461 Apr 28 15:49 field_def_nemo-oce.xml
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 29695 Apr 28 15:49 field_def_nemo-pisces.xml
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 5319 Jul 22 10:46 file_def_nemo_1d_setting.xml
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 5319 Jul 22 10:50 file_def_nemo_1h_setting.xml
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 5319 Aug 2 15:18 file_def_nemo.xml
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 6922 Apr 28 15:49 grid_def_nemo.xml
-rwxr-xr-x 1 jrule n01 1156 May 4 13:52 iodef.xml
```

you will also need a namelist_top_ref and namelist_top_cfg to control the tracers. Before running, set the run information in the namelist_top_cfg. The tracer scenarios are not defined in the namelist file. When running the model will automatically look for a NetCDF file defining the scenario, so make sure you also have this file (eg: Scenario_urea1100_leak1day.nc) in the running directory.

With all files in place you can run the model using a slurm script, eg:

```
sbatch TEST.slurm
```

Notes on generating wiki pdf

Obtain wikidoc code

`git clone https://github.com/jpolton/wikidoc` A handy utility to convert GitHub wiki docs into a PDF. Requires "invisible" HTML tags edits to wiki files. Updated for python3.

Install library

I had to install [wkhtmltopdf](#) . if you are in NOCL, the library is already installed on liv1jobs, load the module with `module load wkhtmltopdf/0.12.6`.

Edit Home.md

Edit Home.md to include HTML header information (as in the wikidoc README)

In particular edit:

- line 2: which include the pdf filename
- line 46: which include the pdf cover title.

E.g.

```
<!-- WIKIDOC CONFIG
--filename SEAsia_Apr22.pdf
--page-size A4
--margin-top 2cm
--margin-left 2cm
--margin-bottom 2cm
--margin-right 2cm
--footer-font-name Verdana
--footer-font-size 6
--footer-spacing 10
--footer-right [page]
WIKIDOC CONFIG -->

<!-- WIKIDOC HTMLHEAD
<html>
<head>
  <STYLE type='text/css'>
    html { font-family: Verdana, Geneva, sans-serif; font-size: 13px; }
    .covertitle { padding-top: 40%; text-align: right; font-size: 40px; }
    .generated { font-size: 12px; }

    table { border-collapse: collapse; margin: 1em auto 1em auto; width: 90%;
border: 1px solid #ccc; }
    tr td:first-child { border-right: 1px solid #ccc; width: 2.5cm !important; }
    table tr:first-child { background-color: #ddd; }
    table td { font-family: Verdana, Geneva, sans-serif; font-size: 8pt; vertical-
align: top; padding: 5px; }

    h1 { page-break-before: always; font-size: 26.6px; }
    h2 { margin-top: 3ex; font-size: 20px; }
    h3 { margin-top: 3ex; font-size: 13.3px; }
```

```

        .breakbefore { page-break-before: always; }
        .wiki_only { display: none; }
    </STYLE>
</head>
<body>
WIKIDOC HTMLHEAD -->

<!-- WIKIDOC HTMLFOOT
</body>
</html>
WIKIDOC HTMLFOOT -->

<!-- the following WIKIDOC comments are optional -->

<!-- WIKIDOC COVER
<div class='covertitle'><b>SEAsia</b> Documentation<br><span class='generated'>generated
from https://github.com/NOC-MSM/SEAsia/wiki: ###_WIKIDOC_GENDATE_###</span></div>
WIKIDOC COVER -->

<!-- WIKIDOC TOCXSL
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<xsl:stylesheet version="2.0"
    xmlns:xsl="http://www.w3.org/1999/XSL/Transform"
    xmlns:outline="http://wkhtmltopdf.org/outline"
    xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
<xsl:output doctype-public="-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Strict//EN"
    doctype-system="http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd"
    indent="yes" />
<xsl:template match="outline:outline">
<html>
<head>
<title>Contents</title>
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<style>
h1 {
    text-align: left;
    font-size: 26.6px;
    font-family: verdana;
}
div {border-bottom: 1px dashed rgb(200,200,200);}
span {float: right;}
li {list-style: none;}
ul {
    font-size: 13px;
    font-family: verdana;
}
ul ul {font-size: 85%; }
ul {padding-left: 0em; }
ul ul {padding-left: 1em;}
a {text-decoration:none; color: black;}
ul.toplevel li { margin-bottom: 1em; }
ul.sublevels li { margin-bottom: 0em; }
ul li:last-child { margin-bottom: 1em; }
</style>
</head>
<body>
<h1>Contents</h1>
<ul class="toplevel"><xsl:apply-templates select="outline:item/outline:item"/></ul>
</body>
</html>
</xsl:template>
<xsl:template match="outline:item">
<li>
<xsl:if test="(@title!='') and (@title!='Contents')">
<div>
<a>

```

```

        <xsl:if test="@link">
            <xsl:attribute name="href"><xsl:value-of select="@link"/></xsl:attribute>
        </xsl:if>
        <xsl:if test="@backLink">
            <xsl:attribute name="name"><xsl:value-of select="@backLink"/></xsl:attribute>
        </xsl:if>
        <xsl:value-of select="@title" />
    </a>
    <span> <xsl:value-of select="@page" /> </span>
</div>
</xsl:if>
<ul class="sublevels">
    <xsl:comment>added to prevent self-closing tags in QtXmlPatterns</xsl:comment>
    <xsl:apply-templates select="outline:item"/>
</ul>
</li>
</xsl:template>
</xsl:stylesheet>
WIKIDOC TOCXSL -->

<!-- end of wikidoc config section -->

```

Add a HTML header to each page

Edit each wiki page, adding

```

<!-- WIKIDOC PDFONLY
<h1>###_WIKIDOC_TITLE_###</h1>
WIKIDOC PDFONLY -->

```

to the top of each page so that the file name is included as the page header

Compile pdf

In a python environment execute the following. (I used python=3.8 but think it was an otherwise vanilla conda environment. E.g. `conda create --name wikidoc_env python=3.8`.

Then `conda activate wikidoc_env`). Then from within the wikidoc repo directory:

```
python wikidoc.py <path-to-wkhtmltopdf> <path-to-wiki-repo>
```

E.g.

```
python wikidoc.py /usr/local/bin/wkhtmltopdf ~/GitHub/SEAsia.wiki
```

The PDF is generated in the repo directory.

If you are in NOCL, log into the livjobs server with `ssh -X livjobs`, and after editing the pages and activating your conda environment, load the libraries with `module load`

`wkhtmltopdf/0.12.6` and run:

```
python wikidoc.py /packages/modules/apps/wkhtmltopdf/0.12.6/local/bin/wkhtmltopdf <path-to-wiki-repo>
```